

StArt - State of the Art through Systematic Review

Title:	Improvements in the resistance of the banana species to Fusarium wilt: A systematic review of methods and perspectives.
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Description:	These articles will be used to carry out a systematic review of the studies carried out in the last ten years on Musa resistance to Fusarium wilt with a focus on the methods and tools adopted.
Objectives:	Identify which are the strategies adopted for the genetic improvement of Musa sp. aiming to mitigate the impact of Fusarium wilt (Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense (Breed 1 and tropical 4)).
Main Question:	<p>Q1. What are the sources of resistance (germplasm) to Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense known?</p> <p>Q2. Which breeding programs work on the resistance to Fusarium wilt with respect to cultivar development?</p> <p>Q3. Which genes are reported associated with resistance to Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense in Musa spp.</p> <p>Q4. What breeding techniques are associated to overcome Fusarium wilt?</p> <p>Q5. Which biotechnological tools are used for assisted selection for resistance to Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense?</p> <p>Q6. Which germplasm collections have information with potential for genetic improvement to Fusarium wilt?</p> <p>Q7. What is the frequency of studies by country and which programs of improvement work with crossbreeding in order to develop resistant cultivars?</p> <p>Q8. Are there scales to assess the disease? What's the difference between them?</p> <p>Q9. How often is the banana genome used?</p>

Keywords: <i>Musa</i> spp., <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>cupense</i> , resistance, genetical enhancement, state-o-art.	
Source Selection Criteria: Only scientific articles.	
Studies Languages: Only English.	
Source Search Methods: Papers found in widely available scientific databases.	
Source Engine: Google Academic; Springer; Portal de Periódicos CAPES; PubMed Central; Web of Science; Scopus.	
Studies inclusion (I) and exclusion criterias (E):	(I) articles that answer the protocol's questions (E) review articles, (E) theses, dissertations, manuals, and book chapters, (E) articles outside the subject, (E) articles published in event annals, (E) articles on genetic diversity of Foc, (E) articles on disease management strategies, and (E) articles on first reports of Foc.
Studies types definition:	Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
Initial studies selection:	Papers that contain in the title, abstract or keywords, the terms <i>Musa</i> spp. and bananas and plantains and <i>Fusarium</i> wilt or <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>cupense</i> or Panama disease and genetic resistance and markers and genes.
Studies quality evaluation:	The objectives and criteria of inclusion and exclusion were previously defined, without ambiguity. Exclusions os papers based on the characteristics/sources of the studies were appropriate.
Information Extraction Fields:	Country of study; area of study; type of test applied; use of the banana genome; genes; techniques and tools; resistance sources; biotechnology.
Results Summarization: In the form of graphs, tables and word cloud.	